

(The spears of the Merciful Party on the Throat of the Servants of the Merciful.) رماح حزب الرحيم على نهور حزب الرحيم

also known as "Rimah Hizbu al-Raheem ala Nuhur Hizb al-Raheem."

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Law, Arabic, Text, Sufism, Language, Islamic Traditions

The text discussed the principles of morality that every Sufi adherent of the Tijjaniyah movement is expected to live by concerning the daily supplications (Dua'a), conjurations (Wurd), and incantations (Zikr) to have the mercy and blessing of the supreme High God. The text analyzed some principles intended to be applied to the Master (Murab), the saints, and fellow Muslims. Other areas are the virtuosity of seeking forgiveness, the word of the divine unity of God, praises to the Prophet Muhammad (SAW), and lastly, the text attest to the general principles of Islam concerning the entire life of a Muslim.

Date Range: 1804 CE - 1903 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: 2012. عمر الفوتي. رماح حزب الرحيم على نهور حزب الرحيم. دار الفكر بيروت لبنان.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.noor-book.com/book/internal_download/b8b9f11e21a072982f964f0d5b93ffc0cf21a7f9/3/d0bad522e6607227bc99149c538t

– Source 1 Description: Noor Book

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: http://www.tariqa-tijaniyya.es/archivos_documentos/Rimah%20-%20Cap.38.pdf

– Source 1 Description: Tariqa Tijaniyya.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

- ↳ Number of sheets
 - Multiple sheets

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: White.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- ↳ Tomb
 - No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No

- ↳ Temple
 - No

- ↳ Shrine
 - No

- ↳ Altar
– No
- ↳ Devotional marker
– No
- ↳ Cenotaph
– No
- ↳ Church
– No
- ↳ Mosque
– Yes
- ↳ Synagogue
– No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
– No
- ↳ Monument
– No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No
- ↳ Cave(s)
– No
- ↳ Hilltops
– No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts
– Yes

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Specify: Bookshop.

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
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↳ Devotional marker
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– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– No

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No

 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No

 - ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - No

 - ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?
 - Yes
-
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
 - No
-
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
 - Yes
-
- ↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?
 - Yes
-
- Yes
-
- ↳ Present full-time?
 - No
-
- ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes
-
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - No
-
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
-
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 30000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 10000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 30000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
– Specify: Deathrate, Birthrate and Migration.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 10000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 8000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Deathrate, Birthrate and Migration.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– No
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
– No
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
– Yes
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No

- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
 - No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

- ↳ Is it orally recited?
 - No

- ↳ Is it read?
 - No

- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: The ritual practice is done through the recitation of praises to the Prophet Muhammad (SAW), utterances of reverence to the High God, and seeking repentance from sin.

- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - Yes

- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - Number of participants: 1000

- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Yes

- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - Number of participants: 2

- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Specify: Three times daily (3).

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– No

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

- ↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?
 - No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?
– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?
– Yes

- ↳ Cultural with religious implications?
 - No

- ↳ Behavioral literature?
 - Yes

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: The text presents the ritual practice of the Tijjaniya Sufi order.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)
– Ritual list

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?
– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?
– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?
– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?
– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?
– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?
– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?
– No

Are formal burials present in the text?
– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?
– No

↳ In cemetery?
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?
– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?
– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Bathing, shrouding, and funeral prayer.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Power of creation.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: The Supreme High God possesses the power to create other beings.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– No

|

↳ In dreams
– No

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists
– Yes

Notes: The Supreme High God communicates through messengers and prophets.

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

Notes: The High God communicates with humans through inspiration.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen
– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: Inspiration.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Mysterious communication to certain people.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Mysterious movement.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Mysterious communication.
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: Supernatural beings worship God the most High.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

↳ Adultery
– Yes

↳ Incest
– Yes

- ↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
– Yes
- ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
– Yes
- ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
– Yes
Notes: A reward is awarded on lawful sex with legal partner.
- ↳ Other sexual practices
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Specify: Supernatural beings care about Animals.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– Yes
Notes: The punishment is on the directives of the High God.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means
– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Other
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group
– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
– No

↳ Other form of punishment
– Specify: Burning in the Hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– Yes

↳ Political failure?
– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?
– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?
– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?
– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: Calamity.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Notes: Angels record good deeds for the High God to award a reward.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
– No

↳ Other?
– Yes

Notes: Eternal residence in paradise.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?
– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– Yes
- ↳ Other?
– Specify: The reward extends to general success in life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
– No
- ↳ At specified time in future
– No
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
– No
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
– No
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Only High God knows the time.

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
– No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
– Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
– No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
– No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
– No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
– No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
– Specify: Hellfire and Paradise.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 5

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 100

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 24

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Trade.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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